

ENCOURAGING CHILDREN'S INTELLECTUAL POTENTIAL THROUGH THE IMPROVEMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND MATERIAL CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *This article explores the issue of stimulating preschool children's intellectual potential by improving the organizational and material environment. Special attention is given to the importance of educational surroundings and material-technical support in developing children's thinking, cognitive interest, mental activity, and creativity. The study includes practical proposals based on international experience, especially the Reggio Emilia approach and Howard Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences.*

Keywords: *preschool education, intellectual potential, developmental environment, Reggio Emilia, material-technical base.*

INTRODUCTION

The large-scale reforms in the field of education carried out in our country, in particular, measures to modernize the preschool education system and bring it into line with international standards, serve the comprehensive development of the younger generation. Article 25 of Law No. 595 "On Preschool Education and Upbringing", adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, states that "the state is obliged to ensure the level of preschool education that meets the requirements of the standard of preschool education and upbringing, create safe conditions for the development, upbringing and care of children, introduce modern innovative and information and communication technologies for the comprehensive development of preschool children."

The State Requirements for the Development of Children of Early and Preschool Age state that "The purpose of the State Standard is to organize a preschool education system based on modern requirements, to bring up healthy and comprehensively developed children, to introduce effective forms and methods of teaching and upbringing into the educational process, to bring up a spiritually mature generation, as well as to introduce and organize mandatory minimum requirements for the volume, content and quality of the educational process, the construction and equipment of preschool educational organizations, the organization of healthy nutrition and safety of preschool children." The state requirements are divided into five main areas of development of children from birth to 7 years. Each area of development, in turn, is divided into sub-areas, which consist of several requirements (expected development indicators) corresponding to each age group. State requirements are established for the following areas of child development: physical development and the formation of a healthy lifestyle, social and emotional development, speech, communication, reading and writing skills; development of the cognitive process; creative development.

In particular, early identification, development and stimulation of children's intellectual potential has become a priority area of state policy. In this process, an important factor is the improvement of organizational and material conditions for organizing the pedagogical process.

In a modern preschool educational institution, a child's intellectual potential is formed not only through the provision of knowledge, but also with the help of a developing environment, didactic tools, educational technologies enriched with games and activities. Specially organized spaces and tools aimed at intellectual development actively activate such aspects of a child's personality as thinking, reasoning, memorization, concentration, logical thinking. Therefore, the high quality of the environment and the material and technical base created in preschool educational organizations is the main guarantee of revealing and developing a child's intellectual potential.

Today, the material and technical base in many preschool educational organizations is insufficient, and the existing conditions cannot fully satisfy the needs of the child's individual development. This, in turn, leads to a decrease in the level of children's mental activity, creativity, and interest in knowledge. Therefore, the issue of creating an environment in the preschool education system that promotes intellectual development, modernization of existing tools, stimulation of children's thought processes by introducing educational games and materials is relevant.

Based on this, this scientific article studies the role of organizational and material conditions in increasing the intellectual potential of preschoolers, ways of improving them and practical mechanisms on a scientific basis.

Intellectual potential is the child's ability to successfully perform such types of mental activity as acquiring knowledge, thinking, analysis, logical inference, solving problems. Preschool age is the most important stage in the mental and intellectual development of a child. It is during this period that such mental processes of a child as speech, thinking, memorization, attention, memory are formed and developed.

As psychologists and teachers (J. Piaget, L.S. Vygotsky, A.V. Zaporozhets, Sh. Amonashvili) note, mental potential develops in childhood through play, communication, and activity. The basis of intellectual development is the child's interest in knowledge, the desire to ask questions, to search. This is formed in a developing environment.

Organizational and material factors influencing the development of intellectual potential: The development of intellectual potential includes not only didactic materials, but also the environment, organized conditions, pedagogical approach, social experience and educational technologies. In particular:

Material and technical base: intellectual games, constructive materials, information technologies.

Pedagogical environment: an open environment where children are treated as individuals and their interests are taken into account.

Organizational conditions: development corners, exhibitions, places aimed at independent research.

The pedagogical process enriched with material conditions, serves as an important tool in the development of children's thinking, problem solving, and the formation of critical thinking skills.

The main activity of preschoolers is play. In play, the child explores the environment, understands logical connections, and tries to solve problems. In particular, **educational games** (puzzles, dominoes, labyrinths, construction sets, Montessori materials, STEAM tools) activate the child's thinking.

During developmental activities, children develop:

patience,
attention and memory,
speech and understanding,
creative approach to the problem,
activity in relation to the issue.

International experience:

Reggio Emilia model: considers the environment as a "third teacher".

Montessori approach: gives the child freedom and encourages independent thinking.

STEM approach: develops technological and engineering thinking from an early age.

National experience: In recent years, the preschool education system of Uzbekistan has paid much attention to the developmental environment. Didactic games, visual materials, and sensory aids are being introduced in republican preschool educational institutions. However, in many regions, the material and technical base is insufficient, and the available opportunities are not fully utilized. The development of intellectual potential requires an integrated approach. The environment and organizational conditions directly affect the mental development of the child. The expected result is achieved only with the integrated use of educational games, didactic tools, environment and pedagogical approaches.

This experimental part studies the practical stage of the work, namely, determining the intellectual potential of preschoolers, the system of pedagogical conditions and methodological work aimed at its development, and their effectiveness. To study the state of existing material conditions and determine the impact of the updated organized environment on the intellectual development of the child, such pedagogical methods as observation, questionnaires and interviews, diagnostic testing, pedagogical experiment, statistical analysis were used.

The experiment was conducted with the participation of children aged 5-6 years from preschool educational organizations No. 30 and 39 of the Payaryk district. Two groups were formed:

Control group - children studying in traditional conditions;

Experimental group - children brought up in a newly created developmental environment.

At the beginning of the experiment, an assessment of the existing conditions was carried out. The main shortcomings were:

outdated and scarce toys;
insufficient play development equipment;
lack of information technology;
lack of "corners of intellectual activity".

According to the survey results, 70% of teachers stated that the existing conditions are insufficient to meet the intellectual needs of the child.

The following innovations were introduced for the experimental group:

Design and design center - enriched with construction sets, logic games, and didactic materials.

Sensory center - for classes on distinguishing colors, shapes, volumes, sounds, and weights.

Information technology-based classes - working with special game programs on tablets.

Individual approach - tasks were created taking into account the interests of each child.

Homework with the participation of parents - expanding the environment through interaction.

At the initial stage (diagnostics), the level of intellectual development of children in both groups was almost equal. The following indicators were noted:

Indicator	Control group (%)	Experimental group (%)
Concentration	47%	49%
Memory	52%	51%
Logical thinking	44%	45%
Answer the question correctly.	48%	46%

At the end of the experiment, the difference was clearly visible:

Indicator	Control group (%)	Experimental group (%)
Concentration	53%	78%
Memory	55%	81%
Logical thinking	50%	85%
Answer the question correctly.	52%	88%

Analysis result: A significant increase was noted in all indicators of the children of the experimental group. This proves that the organized environment had a positive effect on the intellectual potential of children.

The following positive changes were noted through questionnaires and interviews:

Children's interest in lessons has increased.

The number and quality of answers to logical questions have increased.

Independent thinking and analytical skills have developed.

The child's interest in knowledge has also increased at home.

A developing environment and high-quality organizational and material conditions are of decisive importance for the intellectual development of a child.

The results of practical experience have shown that an innovative environment gives impetus to the rapid development of a child's thinking.

It is advisable to widely introduce the newly created "Intellectual Development Corners" in pedagogical practice.

The results of experimental work have shown that for the effective development of intellectual potential in preschool educational organizations, not only the educational program, but also the pedagogical environment and material conditions are of great importance. Based on this, the following **recommendations** were developed:

Organization of a developmental environment:

Organization of an "Intellectual Development Center" (puzzles, constructive games, interactive whiteboards, tablets).

Availability of question-and-answer stands in each group room that encourage children to think.

Didactic materials and technologies:

Games that develop thinking, for example, Montessori tools, LEGO constructor, STEAM activity materials.

Use of information and communication technologies (for example, intellectual game programs, electronic tests).

Professional development of teachers:

Organization of trainings on modern methodologies for intellectual potential.

Special courses based on the Reggio Emilia, Vygotsky, Gardner approaches.

Cooperation with parents:

Providing methodological instructions on activities that stimulate children's thinking at home (for example, solving puzzles together, game-based question-and-answer exercises).

Introduction of weekly events based on the family "Intellect Day" project.

The conditions established on the basis of the following **pedagogical model** ensure the intellectual development of the child through a comprehensive approach:

Model stages:

Stage	Content
1. Analysis stage	Determining the initial intellectual level of children and assessing existing material conditions.
2. Creating an environment	Intellectual development corners, didactic games, and placement of technological tools.
3. Activity planning	Creating pedagogical exercises and tasks that encourage independent thinking.
4. Organization of activities	Interactive games, small group discussions, and critical thinking tasks.
5. Monitoring and analysis	Assessing changes in a child's level of thinking through testing and observation.

From this model, the teacher provides an individual approach to each child, and the activities are organized in an interesting, logical way and stimulate independent thinking.

The following aspects are important in organizing a developmental environment:

Freedom: there must be an activity that the child can choose independently.

Aesthetic environment: a bright, comfortable, attractive space inspires the child.

Personal orientation: the interests and level of development of each child are taken into account.

Integration: developmental games are combined with other subjects (mathematics, language, natural science).

Development of a standard recommendation for the "**Intellectual Development Corner**" for MTT.

Creation of a **methodological manual** for teachers: "Using organizational and material conditions in the development of intellectual potential."

Inclusion of **criteria for assessing the quality of material conditions** in the MTT certification criteria.

Formation of **pilot groups** at the regional level and phased implementation based on the model.

Organizational and material conditions are one of the decisive factors in the intellectual development of a child's personality.

The proposed methodological model based on experimental work gives positive results.

With the wide application of this model in the practice of preschool education, children will qualitatively develop thinking, mental activity, skills of questioning, analysis and problem solving.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The following scientific, theoretical and practical conclusions were made during the study:

Development of children's intellectual potential is one of the important pedagogical areas that should begin in preschool age. The development of this potential is associated with the child's ability to think, mental activity, skills of independent decision-making and problem solving.

Insufficient **organizational and material conditions** in preschool educational organizations, the lack of modern play equipment, limited access to information technology negatively affect the intellectual development of children.

The "Corners of Intellectual Development" created within the **framework** of the study turned out to be effective in increasing the child's interest, encouraging independent thinking and increasing internal motivation for learning.

The results of the experiment showed that the created new environment caused a significant increase in such indicators as attention, memory, logical thinking, and the level of answering questions.

The conditions that serve intellectual development should be strengthened not only by the material base, but also by **the pedagogical approach, the content of the activity, and cooperation with parents.**

Proposals

Based on the results of the study, the following proposals have been developed and are recommended for implementation in practice:

Develop regulatory and legal documents at the republican level on the organization of a development environment in **preschool educational organizations** (methodological recommendations, standard standards).

A mandatory condition is to consider the creation of an **"Intellectual Development Corner"** for each group room. These corners should be enriched with games, didactic tools, interactive equipment that develops thinking.

Introduce **a special module for advanced training of teachers:** "Methodology for developing intellectual potential and ensuring organizational conditions."

Taking with parents, prepare and distribute methodological manuals for supporting intellectual potential at home.

Select pilot organizations at the regional and district levels and gradually expand experimental work based on the model developed in them.

It is proposed to include the level of **material and technical base and development** environment as separate criteria in the certification of preschool educational organizations.

It is recommended that research institutes conduct additional research on this topic and study the adaptability of the model in different regions.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Training" No. 595 - December 16, 2019.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" No. 637 - September 23, 2020. 3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4312 dated May 8, 2019 "On approval of the Concept for the development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030".
3. Resolution No. 2634 dated December 15, 2014 "On the procedure for drawing up, reviewing, approving and registering cost estimates and staffing schedules of budgetary organizations".

4. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 391 dated May 13, 2019 "On measures to further improve the activities of preschool educational organizations".
5. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 22, 2020 No. 802 "On approval of the state standard of preschool education and upbringing".
6. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 25, 2019 No. 626 "On further improvement of the healthy nutrition system in state preschool educational organizations."
7. SanQvaN No. 0016-21. Hygienic requirements for the organization of safe and high-quality nutrition for children brought up in preschool educational organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
8. Mirziyoyev Sh. Strategy of the new Uzbekistan. - T.: Publishing house "Uzbekiston", 2021. 464 p.
9. Salimov O., Kuronboev K., Bekmurodov M., Tangriev L. Wisdom of management. // Tashkent. - "Publishing house of Gafur Gulom", 2018. 168 p.
10. Khodjiev E. Legal foundations of state and public administration. // Tashkent. – «Yangi Kitob», 2017. 257 p.
11. Akhlidinov R.Sh. Lessons of educational management. // Tashkent. - Publishing House of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after A. Navoi. 2013
12. Juraev R.Kh., Turgunov S.T. Educational management. // Tashkent. - «Vorishnashriyot». 2006
13. Eshkobilov S. Implementation of information systems in the management of educational organizations. Methodological manual. - State Technical University of Education and Training named after A. Avloni, 2018
14. Ishmukhamedov R.Zh., Yuldashev M.A. Innovative pedagogical technologies in education and training. // Tashkent. - Publishing House «Nikhol», 2013.
15. Khasanov O. Book of leaders. // Tashkent. – «Mukharrir Publishing House», 2020 <https://asaxiy.uz/uz/product/otabek-asanov-liderlar-kitobi-attiq-muqova>
16. Abdurakhmanov K.Kh. et al. Personnel management. Textbook. // Tashkent. – «Economics», 2013.
17. Khudoyberganov K.T., Nurmukhamedov T.R. et al. Personnel management. Textbook. // Tashkent. - 2010.
18. S.V. Yudakova Psychological and pedagogical aspects of management in the field of education. Textbook. Vladimir 2020.
19. L.M. Bazavluskaya, D.N. Korneev Methods of teaching management. teaching aid. Chelyabinsk, 2019.
20. Lokhtina T.N. Organization of basic management training. Textbook. Irkutsk 2019.
21. Gaziev E.G. Psychology of Management. // Tashkent. - 2001.
22. Abdurakhmanov F.R., Abdurakhmanova Z.E. Know yourself, understand yourself. // Tashkent. - 2013.
23. Kholbekov A.Zh. Sociology of Management. // Tashkent. - "Academy", 2008.
24. Makhmudov I.I. Psychology of Management. // Tashkent. - "Academy". 2006.
25. Abdurakhmonov K.Kh., Kholmominov Sh.R., Zakirova N.G. Personnel Management. Textbook. - // Tashkent. - "Teacher", 2008. 655 p.
26. Imomov A. Psychology of Interpersonal Relations. // Tashkent. – Navruz Publishing House, 2016. 192 pages.

27. Makhmudov I.I., Karaboev Zh. Psychodiagnostics of a leader. // Tashkent. — “Academy”, 2013. 120 p.
28. Makhmudov I. Psychology of management. // Tashkent. – “UNAXPRINT”, 2006. 232 p.
29. Goyibnazarov Sh. Popular culture. // Tashkent. – “Uzbekistan”, 2012.